

Helmholtz Metadata Collaboration

Self-Directed Onboarding Guide for Research Field Matter Data Stewards and Data Managers

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Preamble: Understanding Data Stewardship in Matter Sciences

Effective data stewardship is the foundation for high-quality, reusable, and interoperable research data. Before diving into the matter-specific requirements, it is essential for you as a newly hired data steward or data manager to understand the general principles of data stewardship and research data management (RDM).

This onboarding guide is divided into two parts. The first part of the guide provides a structured introduction to the key responsibilities of data stewards, metadata fundamentals, and open science principles. By gaining a solid understanding of these core concepts, you will be better equipped to implement domain-specific practices, such as data specifications, metadata standards, and policies. The second part of this guide focuses on matter-related challenges, including existing strategies, the NeXus common data format, Electronic Lab Notebooks (ELNs), and relevant policies.

This structured approach ensures you develop the requisite understanding of research data management, enabling them to support researchers effectively and contribute to a sustainable data ecosystem in matter sciences.

Introduction to Data Stewardship

Roles and Responsibilities of Data Stewards/Managers and What is Research Data Management

Objective:

Introduce the role of data stewards, their impact on research, and the fundamentals of RDM.

Recommended course:

<https://moodle.learn.eosc-synergy.eu/course/view.php?id=132§ion=1#tabs-tree-start>

Key topics:

- Definition and scope of the data steward/manager role.
- DMP, Data Policies, FAIR, Open Data, PID etc.

- The importance of data stewardship in research workflows.
- Overview of research data management principles, including the data lifecycle, documentation, and storage.

Metadata Fundamentals

Objective:

Build an understanding of metadata, its purpose, and how to use it effectively.

Recommended course:

HMC - Fundamentals of Metadata

The course is usually offered at least twice a year. Announcements are made via the Helmholtz Metadata Collaboration (HMC) Events webpage and social media channels.

Key topics:

- What is metadata, and why is it important?
- Types of metadata: descriptive, administrative, and structural.
- Common metadata standards and schemas (e.g., Dublin Core, DataCite, domain-specific standards).

Open Science and FAIR Principles

Objective:

Highlight the significance of Open Science and guide participants on implementing the FAIR principles.

Recommended reading:

- <https://forskningsdata.dk/fairytale/index.html%3Fp=140.html>
- <https://faircookbook.elixir-europe.org/content/home.html>

Recommended course:

- <https://www.euniwell.eu/open-science-basic-course>

Key topics:

- Open Science and its benefits
- FAIR principles: making data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable.
- Tools and platforms for implementing FAIR (e.g., repositories, DOIs, and standardized workflows).

Data Sharing and Reusability

Objective:

Equip participants with knowledge about sharing research data effectively and ensuring it can be reused.

Recommended course:

HMC - Reusability of Research Data for Matter: The course is usually offered at least twice a year. Announcements are made via the Helmholtz Metadata Collaboration (HMC) Events webpage and social media channels.

Key topics:

- Strategies for ensuring data is reusable: proper documentation, file formats, and quality checks.
- Reasons/ benefits of data sharing and enabling reusability.
- Legal and ethical considerations in data sharing (e.g., licensing, GDPR compliance).

Matter Specifications for Data Stewards

Investigate existing strategies

Objective:

Discover what data handling methods are already being considered, proposed and implemented by existing projects

Recommended reading:

- DAPHNE4NFDI - Draft recommendations on metadata capture and specifications: <https://zenodo.org/records/12169110>
- Paper: "A Framework for Active DMPs in Photon and Neutron Science Large-Scale Facilities" <https://datascience.codata.org/articles/10.5334/dsj-2024-004>

Key topics:

- Overview of metadata strategies and frameworks in current projects.
- Challenges and solutions in metadata capture and specifications.

Data Infrastructure at Facilities

Objective:

Gain an overview of what the data infrastructure of a research facility is likely to include

Recommended reading:

- HZB Data Infrastructure document: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16312098>

Key topics:

- Types of systems typically found in facilities.
- How data moves through a facility.
- How to find out what applies at a specific facility.

Electronic Lab Notebooks

Objective:

Provide information about available ELNs and necessary features for PaN applications

Recommended reading:

- The ELN Consortium: <https://github.com/TheELNConsortium>
- NOMAD: <https://nomad-lab.eu/prod/v1/docs/> (includes tutorials)
- DAPHNE4NFDI article “Specifications for Electronic Laboratory Notebooks (ELN) in the Photon and Neutron Community”: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/08940886.2024.2432265>
 - “Supplementary Information for Publication: Specifications for Electronic Laboratory Notebooks (ELN) in the Photon and Neutron Community”: <https://zenodo.org/records/13891465>

Key topics:

- Key features of ELNs for photon and neutron science.
- Comparison of different ELNs and their integration with metadata.

Standards

Objective:

Provide information about standards in data management

Recommended reading:

- HMC list of standards for matter: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16321897>

- DCC list of standards: <https://www.dcc.ac.uk/resources/subject-areas/physical-science>
- We will provide a doi link after we publish the standards document that under review now
- Introducing NeXus: <http://www.nexusformat.org/> (<https://manual.nexusformat.org/design.html>)
- Introducing ORSO: https://www.reflectometry.org/advanced_and_expert_level/file_format

Key topics:

- Importance of metadata standards in research data management.
- Domain-specific standards for matter (e.g., NeXus, CIF).
- What is NeXus, and how does it relate to HDF5?
- Structure of a NeXus file: groups, fields, and attributes.
- What is the ORSO format, and how is it used in Python?

Policies in Matter

Objective:

Reference list of data policies in matter at relevant institutes.

Recommended reading:

- **Policies of Helmholtz Matter**
 - DESY: <https://doi.org/10.3204/PUBDB-2025-02454>
 - GSI Helmholtz Centre for Heavy Ion Research (GSI): https://repository.gsi.de/record/339448/files/C-VA-RED-en-Research_Data_Management_Policy.pdf
 - Forschungszentrum Jülich (FZJ): <https://www.fz-juelich.de/en/about-us/management-and-organization/board-of-directors/board-of-directors-office/research-data-policy>
 - Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin (HZB): <https://www.hz-b.de/datapolicy>
 - Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden-Rossendorf (HZDR): <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3698850>
 - Helmholtz-Zentrum Hereon: https://www.hereon.de/imperia/md/content/hzg/forschung/leitlinien-forschungsdatenmanagement-hzg_03-2019.pdf
 - Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT): <https://www.rdm.kit.edu/downloads/KIT-RDM-Policy.pdf>
- **Policies of External Bodies**
 - PaNOSC FAIR Research data policy framework: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3862701>

- Comment on the PaNOSC Data Policy Framework: R. Krahl (2020). Internal project communication. <https://nubes.helmholtz-berlin.de/s/d8irXC2zdPH2Tbb>
- ExPaNDS Guidance Note - Key Policy Elements within a Photon and Neutron Research Infrastructure Data Policy Framework: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6090282>

Key topics:

- Matter specific data policy elements
- Overview of data policies in research institutions.
- Data sharing requirements and open-access mandates.

Training Resources

Objective:

Places to look for further training in specific areas.

Recommended reading:

- HIDA Course Catalog: <https://www.helmholtz-hida.de/course-catalog/en/>
- PaNOSC: <https://www.panosc.eu/> (Section for Training, but general for all PaN disciplines: <https://pan-training.eu/>)

Key topics:

- Available training platforms for research data management (HIDA, PaNOSC).
- Online courses and workshops for metadata and data stewardship

Contacts

E-mail: hmc-matter@helmholtz-berlin.de

Address:

Helmholtz Metadata Collaboration (HMC)
Hub Matter / Hub Information
Helmholtz Zentrum Berlin (HZB)
Hahn-Meitner-Platz 1
14109 Berlin